

Access, Usage, and Satisfaction: A Study of E-Resource Utilization at the District Central Library, Vijayanagar

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Abstract

Public libraries are transforming due to advancements in computing and telecommunication technologies. To remain relevant and resourceful in the digital age, libraries must integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into their core services. This integration enhances access to resources, improves service delivery, and extends services to remote and underserved populations. A study at the District Central Library in Vijayanagar, Karnataka, found that over two-fifths of respondents visit the library daily, with half reporting intermediate digital skills. The study emphasizes the growing role of ICT in public library services and the need for continued investment in infrastructure, user education, and digital literacy.

Keywords: Public libraries, e-resources, user satisfaction, digital information services, ICT in libraries, information access, library usage patterns

1. Introduction

Public libraries, particularly in India, play a crucial role in social change, education, and information dissemination. They empower individuals through knowledge and access to information. To remain effective in the digital era, libraries must adopt computing and telecommunication technologies. With rapid advancements in ICT, libraries are embracing automation and digitalization, improving services and reaching remote areas. Public libraries are now recognized as the most appropriate mechanism to channel information and motivate information seekers. They are increasingly becoming digital gateways, linking users to regional and national information networks through modern technology. The focus of library digitization has expanded to include digital resource access, online services, remote connectivity, and user-centered platforms. The evolving role of public libraries calls for strategic planning and investment to fully integrate digital resources and enhance user experiences.

2. Objectives

- To assess the level of awareness among users regarding the availability of e-resources.
- To evaluate users' digital literacy and skill levels in accessing and utilizing e-resources effectively.

- To measure user satisfaction with the quality, accessibility, and relevance of the digital information resources and services.
- To identify challenges and barriers faced by users in accessing e-resources.

3. Materials and Methods

The present study a survey method using a structured questionnaire to collect data. A total of 185 questionnaires were randomly distributed to users of the District Central Library, Vijayanagar, Karnataka. Out of these, 155 completed questionnaires were returned. However, 30 questionnaires were excluded due to incomplete responses. Therefore, a total of 140 valid questionnaires were used for data analysis and interpretation. The primary data collection was conducted on July 14, 2025.

4. Data analysis and interpretation

Table 1: Gender-wise Distribution

S. No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Male	91	58.71%
2	Female	64	41.29%
Total		155	100%

Fig 1: Gender-wise Distribution

The study has identified Out of the total 155 respondents, the highest Frequency were male, accounting for 91 individuals or (58.71%) of the sample. Female respondents numbered 64, making up (41.29%) of the total. This indicates that male users of the District Central Library, Vijayanagar, are more actively engaged in accessing or utilizing the library's e-resources.

Fig 2: Age-wise Distribution

Provides clear insights that, accounting for 91 individuals or (58.71%) of the sample. Female respondents numbered 64, making up (41.29%) of the total. This indicates that male users of the District Central Library, Vijayanagar, are more actively engaged in accessing or utilizing the library's e-resources compared to their female counterparts. The gender gap, though not extremely wide, suggests a need for targeted outreach or support to encourage greater participation of female users in digital library services.

Table 2: Age-wise Distribution

S. No	Age Group (Years)	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Below 15	8	5.16%
2	16 to 20	16	10.32%
3	21 to 30	27	17.42%
4	31 to 40	52	33.55%
5	41 to 50	15	9.68%
6	51 and above	37	23.87%
Total		155	100%

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

S. No	Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	SSLC	21	13.55%
2	HSC	13	8.39%
3	U.G	39	25.16%
4	P.G	23	14.84%
5	M. Phil	15	9.68%
6	Ph.D.	11	7.10%
7	Diploma	8	5.16%
8	Others	25	16.13%
Total		155	100%

Fig 3: Educational Qualification

Table 3 shows the respondents in the study are graduates, accounting for 25.16% of the total, followed by "Others" (16.13%) and postgraduates (14.84%). The library's e-resources are primarily used by academics seeking information for study, research, or career development. SSLC (13.55%) and HSC (8.39%) users also make up a

significant portion, indicating its wide educational spectrum. M.Phil (9.68%) and Ph.D. (7.10%) users engage with e-resources, highlighting their academic relevance. Diploma holders (5.16%) form the smallest group, possibly due to their technical or practical focus.

Table 4: Frequency of Visiting the Library

S. No	Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Daily	63	40.65%
2	Once in a week	38	24.52%
3	Twice in a week	27	17.42%
4	Monthly	16	10.32%
5	Rarely	11	7.10%
Total		155	100%

Fig 4: Visiting the Library

Table 4 highlights the District Central Library, Vijayanagar, has a high level of regular engagement with its digital offerings, with (40.65%) of respondents accessing them daily. Over 82% of users engage with these resources at least weekly, indicating consistent and meaningful usage.

However, less frequent use is reported on a monthly basis (10.32%), and only 7.10% use them rarely, possibly due to limited digital literacy, reduced need, or lack of awareness of available content. Overall, the library's e-resources are an integral part of users' routines.

Table 5: Purpose of Visiting the Library

S. No	Purpose	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	To borrow and return books	26	16.77%
2	To read newspapers/magazines/employment information	21	13.55%
3	To consult reference books	19	12.26%
4	To read general books	30	19.35%
5	To read subject books	23	14.84%
6	To complete classroom assignments	19	12.26%
7	To use Internet	12	7.74%
9	To know the latest arrivals in the library	3	1.94%
10	Others (if any)	2	1.29%
Total		155	100%

Fig 5: Purpose of Visiting Library

Table 5 presents the responses of the District Central Library in Vijayanagar, India, is visited by a diverse group of users, with the most common purpose being general reading (19.35%). Other common activities include borrowing and returning books (16.77%), reading subject-specific books (14.84%), accessing newspapers/magazines/employment information (13.55%), consulting reference books and completing classroom assignments (12.26%). The library effectively serves both students and general knowledge seekers. However, only 7.74% of users use the internet, suggesting limited digital

infrastructure, preference for physical materials, or lack of digital skills. The least cited purposes knew the latest arrivals (1.94%) and others (1.29%).

Table 6: Category of Use of Digital Sources Skill

S. No	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Beginner	61	39.35%
2	Intermediate	73	47.10%
3	Expert	21	13.55%
Total		155	100%

Fig 6: Use of Digital Sources Skill

Table 6 displays, 155 respondents are in the Intermediate category (47.10%), with 73 users having moderate proficiency in using e-resources. The Beginner category (39.35%) has 61 users learning to navigate and fully utilize

the library's digital resources. Only 21 users (13.55%) are considered experts, indicating a small but important segment of the user base.

Table 7: Purpose of Using Internet

S. No	Purpose	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Preparation of exam	66	42.58%
2	Research purpose	15	9.68%
3	Entertainment	28	18.06%
4	News	19	12.26%
6	Preparation for seminar/conference	8	5.16%
7	To write and publish papers	4	2.58%
8	Any other	15	9.68%
Total		155	100%

Fig 7: Using Internet

Table 7 displays the specific the respondents of (47.10%) identify as intermediate users of e-resources, indicating moderate digital literacy. 39.35% consider themselves beginners, requiring basic skills training and user-friendly interfaces. Only 13.55% classify themselves as experts, suggesting that the overall population would benefit from capacity building and awareness programs to advance their digital proficiency. The data suggests that a small group of highly skilled users may require more guidance to fully benefit from available e-resources.

5. Major findings of the study

- Gender: Majority of respondents were male 58.71%, while females accounted for 41.29%.
- Age Group: The largest group was aged 31 to 40 years 33.55%, followed by 51 and above 23.87%. Younger respondents (below 15) were the least represented 5.16%.
- Qualification: Most respondents held an undergraduate degree 25.16%, followed by others 16.13% and postgraduate degrees 14.84%.
- Daily users formed the largest group 40.65%, followed by those accessing e-resources once a week 24.52%.
- Less frequent usage was reported monthly 10.32% and rarely 7.10%.

- The primary purpose was reading general books 19.35% and borrowing/returning books 16.77%.
- Other common reasons included reading newspapers/magazines/employment info 13.55% and reading subject books 14.84%.
- Internet use through the library accounted for 7.74%.
- Nearly half of the users 47.10% identified as intermediate in using e-resources, while beginners made up 39.35%. Expert users accounted for 13.55%.
- The major specific purpose was preparation for exams 42.58%, followed by entertainment 18.06% and news reading 12.26%.
- Research purposes and other academic activities accounted for smaller proportions.
- The frequency and variety of purposes indicate strong engagement and varied utility of the e-resources.
- Satisfaction levels can be inferred as positive, given the daily and weekly usage trends.

6. Conclusion

The study on e-resource utilization at the District Central Library in Vijayanagar reveals that the library is crucial in providing digital access to diverse user groups, including daily and weekly users. The majority of users are

intermediate-level, indicating a potential user base that could benefit from further training. The primary uses of e-resources include exam preparation, reading general and subject books, and accessing current news. The findings suggest that continued investment in enhancing e-resource availability, user training, and infrastructure will strengthen the library's impact in the community.

7. References

1. Malipatil B, Mallikarjun V. Use of E-Resources: User Satisfaction with the District Central Library, Raichur-Karnataka [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371474839>
2. Bertot JC, Jaeger PT, Langa E, McClure CR. Public access computing and Internet access in public libraries: The role of public libraries in e-government and emergency situations. *Government Information Quarterly*. 2006;11(9).
3. Maraddi KS. Impact of E-Resources among the research students of University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur. In: *Integrating ICT in Academic Libraries: Making a Difference in Knowledge Age*. c2014. p. 117–123. ISBN: 978-8192756912.
4. Velmurugan C. Use and user perception on electronic resources in the academic community. In: *Creativity, Innovation and Transformation in Libraries*. SALIS 2016, Chennai; c2016. p. 154–156.
5. Marjaei S, Ahmadianyazdi F, Chandrashekara M. Awareness and satisfaction of research scholars using library resources and services in academic libraries. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 2022. p. 1–8.
6. Omeiza JV, Oluwabunmi BD. Evaluation of the use of university library resources and services by the students of Lead City University: A case study of nursing students. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 2021. p. 1–15.
7. Thiyagarajah R, Sarjit SG. The English reading habits of ELLS students in University Science Malaysia. *ULTIBASE Articles* [Internet]. 1999 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: <http://ultibase.rmit.edu.au/Articles/may00/thiyag1.htm>
8. Whitmire E. Academic library performance measures and undergraduates' library use and educational outcomes. *Library & Information Science Research*. 2002;24(2):107–128.
9. Dauda J. Users' assessment of e-resources at the university library of the University of the Philippines, Diliman. *Journal of Philippine Librarianship*. 2014;34:1–13.
10. Haque MA, Hoq KMG. Student perception of electronic resources use in Rajdhani University Library: A case study. *International Journal of Information and Library Science*. 2018;10(7):78–84.
11. Mawere T, Sai K. An investigation on e-resource utilization among university students in a developing country: A case of Great Zimbabwe University. *South African Journal of Information Management*. 2018;20(1):1–7. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajim.v20i1.860>

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